

Long-Term Effect of Message Framing on Perceived Vulnerability and Environmental Responsibility: The Moderating Role of Self-Efficacy

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Abstract

In a context where environmental communication seeks to produce lasting rather than immediate change, it is essential to understand how messages influence attitudes and behaviors over time. The objective of this study was to examine the long-term effects of message framing (positive vs. negative) on perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility, while incorporating self-efficacy as a moderating factor. To do this, a laboratory experiment was conducted with 146 students, with data collected at two separate times: immediately after exposure to the message, and then three months later to assess the persistence of the effects. The results indicate that, in the long term, negative framing has a more pronounced impact on perceived vulnerability than positive framing. However, no significant difference was observed between the two experimental conditions with regard to environmental responsibility. Furthermore, the analyses show that perceived vulnerability plays a complete mediating role in the relationship between the type of framing and environmental responsibility. Finally, the findings reveal that self-efficacy positively moderates the relationship between perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility: the more individuals feel capable of taking action, the more perceived vulnerability contributes to strengthening their responsible engagement.

Keywords: *Message framing; longitudinal approach; perceived vulnerability; environmental responsibility; self-efficacy.*

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Introduction

Beyond debates on the best environmental communication strategies, one central question remains: how can formulate a message that not only captures the public's attention, but also supports the sustainable adoption of environmentally responsible behaviors? In a context where climate issues require profound and continuous change, understanding the psychological mechanisms underlying the reception and effectiveness of messages becomes essential. Among these mechanisms, the framing of information plays a key role.

In environmental communication research, framing in terms of gains or losses is one of the most widely explored equivalence mechanisms (Cacciatore et al., 2016). Gain framing messages highlight the benefits

of adopting a desired behavior, while loss framing messages emphasize the risks or negative consequences associated with inaction (Tversky & Kahneman, 1985). Several studies suggest that loss framing message is more effective than gain framing message (Chen, 2016; Moon et al., 2016; Zhou and Wang, 2022). At the same time, numerous studies indicate that the perception of risk does not systematically lead to protective behavior (Bamberg et al., 2017; van Valkengoed and Steg, 2019). One of the key factors explaining this discrepancy is individuals' level of self-efficacy: the perceived ability to act strongly influences the likelihood of adopting behaviors (Bagagnan et al., 2019; Ghanian et al., 2020).

Despite the contribution of this research, the majority of studies focus primarily on the immediate effects of framing, without considering the sustainability or stability of the changes observed. However, in areas where behavioral continuity is essential, such as environmental action, the question of the persistence of effects is a fundamental issue. While the importance of longitudinal data is widely recognized for studying the dynamics of risk perceptions and behaviors (Bubeck et al., 2020; Kuhlicke et al., 2020), to the best of our knowledge, few studies have used it to analyze the impacts of message framing, practically in environmental context. Consequently, this research aims to fill these gaps by adopting a longitudinal approach to determine whether loss-oriented frames have a more lasting influence than gain-oriented frames, incorporating self-efficacy as a moderator. On the basis of these objectives, several research questions structure and guide this study.

- Does negative message framing produce greater long-term effects on perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility than positive message framing?
- Does perceived vulnerability influence environmental responsibility?
- RQ3: Does self-efficacy moderate the effect of perceived vulnerability on environmental responsibility?

Literature Review

Message framing refers to a “*type of linguistic expression involving the sharing of information with similar meanings through different information-encoding methods, such as diction and tone, thus affecting the processing and decoding of the content by the audience, resulting in different cognitions and judgments*” (Van de Velde et al., 2010). In other words, the form given to information influences the way it is perceived and interpreted. Framing can be positive—highlighting the benefits of a behavior—or negative, emphasizing the losses or consequences associated with inaction. Framing plays a central role in consumers' behavioral decisions (Levin et al., 1988). Negative message frames, for example, describe the adverse repercussions of a behavior or situation (Gerend and Cullen, 2008). They tend to elicit emotions such as guilt or shame, which can motivate behavioral change (Amatulli et al., 2019).

In the field of environmental communication, framing in terms of gains or losses is one of the most widely studied equivalence frameworks (Cacciatore et al., 2016). Messages framed in terms of gains emphasize the benefits associated with desired behavior, while messages focused on losses emphasize the risks or negative consequences of inaction (Tversky and Kahneman, 1985). Research by Van de Velde et al. (2010) shows that messages focused on gains can increase the public's sensitivity to information, reinforce their perception of the credibility of the content, and encourage purchase intentions. However, other research indicates that loss-oriented framing may be more persuasive in certain contexts, particularly for the promotion of health products (Chen, 2016) or environmentally friendly biofuels (Moon et al., 2016). Moreover, several studies suggest that negative framing can be more persuasive than positive framing, as it triggers strong emotions such as fear, anger or feelings of vulnerability, which are perceived as signals of threat that can motivate action (Chang and Wu, 2015; Zhou and Wang, 2022).

Prospect theory (Tversky and Kahneman, 1985) offers an explanation for these differences in effectiveness. It suggests that individuals display a marked asymmetry in their reaction to gains and losses: when faced with options involving gains, they tend to avoid risk and favour a certain profit; on the other hand, when a situation involves losses, they are more inclined to accept risk in order to avoid a certain loss. Furthermore, human sensitivity to losses is generally stronger than to equivalent gains (Hardisty and Weber, 2009). This aversion to losses explains why messages focused on loss can elicit more intense negative emotions, reinforce pessimistic perceptions and improve attention to content, thereby facilitating the acceptance of information (Chen, 2016). In the field of prosocial behavior, Bullard and Penner (2017) have shown, for example, that evoking the negative consequences of inaction — such as not buying environmentally friendly products or not contributing to charitable causes — can activate fear and encourage more responsible decisions. Recently, Zhou and Wang (2022) showed that negative anthropomorphic message framing positively influences perceived vulnerability.

Despite the interest of these studies, most of them focus mainly on the immediate or short-term effects of framing, without examining the duration or stability of the observed impacts. However, the question of the persistence of effects is a crucial issue, particularly in areas where the sustainable adoption of behavior is essential, such as environmental protection or prosocial engagement. Given individuals' increased sensitivity to negative information and the potential for loss-focused messages to generate strong reactions—it is plausible that this type of framing produces more lasting effects than gain-focused messages. From this perspective, it is reasonable to postulate that loss-oriented framing could exert a more sustained influence over time and thus prove more effective in the long term than gain-oriented framing. Based on these theoretical considerations, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H1: The long-term effect of negative message frame on perceived vulnerability is greater than the effect produced by positive message frame.

H2: The long-term effect of negative message frame on environmental responsibility is greater than the effect produced by positive message frame.

Vulnerability relates to “*how people feel in the face of adverse circumstances*” (Zhou and Wang, 2022). It is considered a state of fragility or impairment of one's ability to act, and it confers increased responsibility towards those deemed particularly vulnerable (Gross and McGoey, 2015). In the environmental field, individuals who are aware of the vulnerability of the environment develop a stronger sense of responsibility towards it, leading them to favor environmentally friendly purchasing behaviors (Channa et al., 2022). Other studies have also shown that individuals feel more responsible and inclined to help those they perceive as vulnerable (Chasteen and Madey, 2003; Moche and Västfjäll, 2021). When environmental issues are anthropomorphised, i.e. when the environment is represented as a human entity, individuals tend to treat it as a person. This personification strengthens their emotional commitment and encourages them to adopt pro-environmental behaviors (Zhou and Wang, 2022). Furthermore, environmental issues are considered more important by individuals with a high perception of environmental threats, which increases their motivation to act in favor of the environment (O'Connor et al., 1999). In the same vein, Wang et al. (2019) demonstrated that perceived vulnerability positively influences farmers' intention to adopt environmental practices, while Zhou and Wang (2022) confirmed its favorable effect on environmental responsibility. Consequently, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3: Perceived vulnerability positively influences environmental responsibility

In the current context of intensifying climate impacts, understanding why some people adopt pro-environmental behaviors while others remain inactive remains a central question for social and environmental sciences. Individual perceptions of risk are a key element in this decision-making process, but they alone are not sufficient to explain the adoption of protective behaviors. This is leading more and more researchers to examine the psychological conditions that may influence how these perceptions

translate—or do not translate—into concrete actions. Numerous studies have shown that the perception of climate risk does not systematically lead individuals to adopt measures to protect themselves (Bamberg et al., 2017; van Valkengoed & Steg, 2019). The protection motivation theory (Rogers, 1983) provides a relevant framework for understanding this dynamic: it posits that the link between risk perception and behavior depends in particular on the degree to which individuals feel capable of carrying out the necessary actions, i.e. their self-efficacy (Bagagnan et al., 2019; Ghanian et al., 2020). Thus, even when a climate threat is clearly identified, a low level of self-efficacy can prevent individuals from implementing measures that are nevertheless considered relevant (van Valkengoed et al., 2024).

Although it is widely admitted that self-efficacy can play a moderating role between risk perception and behavior (van Valkengoed et al., 2024), another factor deserves attention: previous behavioral experience. People who have already adopted adaptation or protection measures tend to have higher levels of self-efficacy, as they have already proven their ability to take action and have seen the effects of these actions on reducing climate impacts (Samaddar et al., 2014; van Valkengoed et al., 2024). This dimension suggests that self-efficacy not only determines the transition from perception to action, but may also play a role in other psychological relationships related to environmental behavior. From this perspective, it is plausible to consider that self-efficacy can moderate the link between perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility. On this basis, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Self-efficacy moderates the relationship between perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility.

Figure1. Conceptual Model

Methodology

Design and Participants

This study is based on a laboratory experiment designed to examine the effect of message framing (positive vs. negative) on perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility. Two experimental conditions were created: positive framing, where a video highlighted the benefits of adopting pro-environmental behaviors, and negative framing, where a video emphasized the potential consequences of inaction in the face of climate risks. Both videos were created specifically for this research: they each last about 8 minutes, feature the same narrator, the same visual style (illustrative images of climate change, scenes from everyday life) and follow the same structure (introduction of the problem, presentation of the impacts, highlighting mitigation and adaptation behaviors). The factual content (climate data, examples of consequences and recommended behaviors) is strictly identical in both versions; only the wording changes in order to manipulate the framing of the message, with the positive version emphasizing the gains and improvements possible if action is taken, and the negative version highlighting the potential losses and damage if no action is taken. The factual content (climate data, examples of

consequences and recommended behaviors) is strictly identical in both versions; only the wording changes in order to manipulate the framing of the message, with the positive version emphasizing the gains and improvements possible if action is taken, and the negative version highlighting the potential losses and damage if no action is taken. The sound level, duration, rhythm of speech and montage are harmonized in order to control the effects related to the form of the message. The videos are pre-tested with a small sample group to verify that they are perceived as positively or negatively framed, and that they are judged to be comparable in terms of clarity, credibility and interest.

Participants are recruited from among students at a Tunisian university via advertisements posted on institutional platforms. Participation is entirely voluntary and does not involve any academic or financial compensation, in order to avoid any pressure or selection bias. Before the study begins, each participant receives comprehensive information about the general objectives of the research and signs an informed consent form. Responses are collected on a strictly anonymous basis, with no data that could identify participants being recorded. Participants are assigned to the two experimental conditions (positive framing vs. negative framing) at random using a computerized number generator, ensuring a balanced distribution and limiting systematic bias between groups. The experiment is conducted in a laboratory to ensure optimal control of the environment and exposure to the videos. Data was collected at two points in time: immediately after viewing the video, to assess the immediate effects of message framing on perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility, and again three months later, to measure the persistence of these effects and the effect of self-efficacy.

Measures

Perceived vulnerability was assessed using four items adapted from the work of Workman et al. (2008) and Shafiei and Maleksaeidi (2020). These items measure participants' perceptions of their potential exposure to the impacts of climate change and the likelihood that they will suffer its effects. Responses were collected on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = 'strongly disagree', 7 = 'strongly agree') ($\alpha = 0.911$). *Environmental responsibility* was measured using three items from the scale developed by Stone et al. (1995). This measure assesses the degree to which participants feel they have a personal responsibility to protect the environment ($\alpha = 0.904$). Participants responded to the items on a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 'strongly disagree' to 7 'strongly agree'. *Self-efficacy* specific to managing climate change threats was assessed using a single item developed by van Valkengoed et al. (2024). This item measures participants' perceptions of their ability to take effective action to reduce climate risks. The response scale ranges from 1 ('strongly disagree') to 7 ('strongly agree').

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

A total of 148 students took part in the study. Two of them did not complete the final assessment conducted three months after the intervention, bringing the final sample to 146 participants who completed the entire protocol. Demographic data (see Table 1) show that the average age of participants was 25.11 years. The gender distribution was relatively balanced, with 51.4% women and 48.6% men. In terms of educational level, the study population consisted mainly of bachelor's degree students (43.9%), followed by those enrolled in master's programs (34.9%) and doctoral students (21.2%).

Table 1. Demographic Profile

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Woman	75	51.4
	Men	71	48.6

Education level	Bachelor's degree	64	43.9
	Master's degree	51	34.9
	Doctoral degree	31	21.2
Age		Mean 25.11	Range 20-31 Years

Hypotheses Testing

In order to examine the first two hypotheses, two mixed analyses of variance (repeated measures ANOVA) were performed. The type of message framing (positive vs. negative), was included as a between-subjects indicator. The timing of the assessment—immediately after exposure and then three months later—was used as a within-subjects indicator.

The results of first analyses (see Table 2) highlight a significant main effect of message framing on perceived vulnerability: participants who received a negatively framed message reported higher levels of vulnerability than those who were exposed to a positively framed message ($M_{Negative\ message\ frame} = 4.49$ vs. $M_{Positive\ message\ frame} = 3.34$; $F = 33.793$, $p < 0.01$, $\eta^2 = 0.150$). A main effect of time also appears, showing an overall decrease in perceived vulnerability three months after exposure compared to the measurement taken immediately after exposure ($M_{Immediately} = 4.13$ vs. $M_{Three-months\ later} = 3.68$; $F = 30.396$, $p < 0.01$, $\eta^2 = 0.174$). In addition, a significant interaction between the type of message framing (positive vs. negative) and the timing of the assessment was observed ($F = 4.443$, $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.030$). To analyze this interaction in more detail, paired t-tests were performed. As shown in Table 2, a significant decrease in perceived vulnerability between the two measurement times was only observed among participants who received a positive message ($t = 2.851$, $p < 0.01$). Conversely, no significant variation was observed among participants exposed to the negative framing message ($t = 1.329$, $p > 0.05$). These results suggest that despite the decrease observed in the negative message condition, the level of perceived vulnerability measured three months later remains higher than that observed in the positive message condition, which supports *hypothesis H1*.

The results of second analyses (see Table 2) highlight a significant main effect of message framing on environmental responsibility: participants who received a negatively framed message reported higher levels of environmental responsibility than those who were exposed to a positively framed message ($M_{Negative\ message\ frame} = 3.56$ vs. $M_{Positive\ message\ frame} = 3.17$; $F = 4.915$, $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.033$). A main effect of time also appears, showing an overall decrease in environmental responsibility three months after exposure compared to the measurement taken immediately after exposure ($M_{Immediately} = 3.52$ vs. $M_{Three-months\ later} = 3.21$; $F = 7.551$, $p < 0.01$, $\eta^2 = 0.050$). However, the interaction between the type of message framing (positive vs. negative) and the timing of the assessment was not significant ($F = 0.195$, $p > 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.001$). These results suggest that the effect of message framing on environmental responsibility does not vary significantly over time. Consequently, *hypothesis H2* was not supported.

Table 2. Results of Mixed-ANOVA Analyses and Paired Samples T-Test

Mixed ANOVA		Dependent variables							
		<i>Perceived vulnerability</i>				<i>Environmental responsibility</i>			
		M	F	p	η^2	M	F	p	η^2
Message framing	Positive (N=74)	3.34	33.793	0.000	0.190	3.17	4.915	0.028	0.033
	Negative (N=72)	4.49				3.56			
Time	Immediately	4.13	30.396	0.000	0.174	3.52	7.551	0.007	0.050
	Three-months later	3.68				3.21			

Message framing*	Time	Positive	3.65	4.443	0.037	0.030	3.35	0.195	0.660	0.001
		Negative	4.63				3.69			
*	Three-months later	Positive	3.03	4.35	0.037	0.030	2.99	0.195	0.660	0.001
		Negative	4.35				3.43			

Paired samples t-test		Perceived vulnerability		
Message framing	Time	M	T	p
Positive (N=74)	Immediately	3.65	2.851	0.004
	Three-months later	3.03		
Negative (N=72)	Immediately	4.63	1.329	0.186
	Three-months later	4.35		

To assess hypotheses H3 and H4, moderate mediation analysis was estimated using the PROCESS macro (model 14) with 5.000 *bootstrap*. The results, illustrated in Figure 2, indicate first that message framing (positive vs. negative) has a positive and significant long-term effect on perceived vulnerability ($\beta = 0.54$; $p < 0.01$; 95%CI = 0.34; 0.74). In turn, perceived vulnerability positively predicts environmental responsibility ($\beta = 0.33$; $p < 0.01$; 95% CI = 0.21; 0.45), thus supporting *hypothesis H3*. However, the direct effect of message framing on environmental responsibility is not significant ($\beta = 0.06$; $p > 0.05$; 95%CI= -0.03; 0.15). The indirect effect, on the other hand, appears significant only among individuals with high levels of self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.21$; $p < 0.01$; 95% CI = 0.013; 0.29). These findings suggest that perceived vulnerability plays a complete mediating role in the relationship between message framing and environmental responsibility. Furthermore, the analyses highlight a significant interaction between perceived vulnerability and self-efficacy in predicting environmental responsibility ($M \times W = 0.19$; $p < 0.05$; 95% CI = 0.11; 0.27). In other words, self-efficacy reinforces the influence of perceived vulnerability: the more individuals feel capable of taking the necessary actions, the stronger the relationship between their sense of vulnerability and their level of environmental responsibility. These results therefore support *hypothesis H4*.

Figure 2. Moderated Mediation Analysis

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that negative framing have a more pronounced long-term effect on perceived vulnerability than positive framing. This finding is consistent with numerous studies highlighting the persuasive superiority of negative framing in environmental communications. In particular, several studies have shown that messages focused on losses or risks elicit more intense emotions, including feelings of vulnerability, which increases their psychological impact (Chang & Wu,

2015; Zhou & Wang, 2022). More recently, Zhou and Wang (2022) have shown that negative framing applied to anthropomorphic messages intensifies the perception of vulnerability. The results obtained in the present study confirm these observations by showing that the amplifying effect of negative framing persists even several months after initial exposure. However, the analysis reveals no significant difference between positive and negative framing in terms of their long-term effect on environmental responsibility. This result contrasts in part with some previous studies suggesting that loss-focused messages are more effective in promoting environmental behaviours or intentions, as observed by Moon et al. (2016) in the field of biofuel promotion. Nevertheless, one possible explanation lies in the fact that the effect of negative framing is more likely to be triggered by emotional mechanisms, such as perceived vulnerability, which are not always sufficient to trigger lasting behavioral change. In other words, even if negative framing elicits a stronger emotional response, this does not necessarily translate into increased environmental engagement in the long term, which could explain the lack of difference observed between the two types of messages framing.

Furthermore, the results confirm that perceived vulnerability is a positive determinant of environmental responsibility. This relationship is consistent with the work of Wang et al. (2019), who showed that the perception of an environmental threat positively influences farmers' intention to adopt more sustainable practices. Similarly, Zhou and Wang (2022) demonstrated that perceived vulnerability positively influences environmental responsibility among individuals exposed to anthropomorphic climate messages. The data collected in this study align with these findings, suggesting that awareness of a personal or collective threat can act as a motivational lever for responsible behavior.

Finally, the results show that self-efficacy plays an essential moderating role in the link between perceived vulnerability and environmental responsibility. This observation resonates with a body of work demonstrating that risk perception, in order to be truly translated into action, must be accompanied by a sense of personal capacity to act (Bagagnan et al., 2019; Ghanian et al., 2020). Thus, even when individuals perceive a climate threat, those who feel unable to act are likely to remain passive, as recently pointed out by van Valkengoed et al. (2024). The study therefore shows that perceived vulnerability only leads to increased environmental responsibility when individuals have a sufficiently high level of self-efficacy to consider taking concrete action.

Conclusion

The results of this study make several important contributions to the literature on the framing of environmental messages and the psychological mechanisms underlying pro-environmental behavior. Firstly, the evidence of the lasting effect of negative framing on perceived vulnerability enriches theoretical models of persuasive communication, particularly those that emphasize the importance of risk-related emotions. While most studies focus on immediate effects, this research shows that the emotional reactions elicited by negative framing persist over time, suggesting that explanatory models should give greater consideration to the temporal dimension when studying cognitive and affective responses to environmental messages. Secondly, the lack of a differential effect of framing on long-term environmental responsibility challenges certain theoretical assumptions that loss-focused messages are systematically more effective at triggering pro-environmental behaviors. The results suggest a more nuanced view, clearly distinguishing between the emotional reaction (vulnerability) and the actual adoption of responsibility or behavior. This suggests that simply increasing perceived vulnerability is insufficient to produce a lasting behavioral effect without the presence of mediating or moderating variables, such as self-efficacy. Thirdly, this study reinforces the central role of perceived vulnerability as a psychological mechanism influencing environmental responsibility, confirming its relevance in integrative models of ecological behavior. By adding the moderating effect of self-efficacy, the results enrich existing theories, particularly those based on Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), by

emphasizing that pro-environmental motivation depends on the interaction between risk perception and perceived personal capabilities. This is an original contribution that clarifies why some threat-based messages work for some audiences but not for others.

From a managerial perspective, the results of this study offer key recommendations for those involved in environmental communication, whether public organizations, NGOs, businesses or awareness campaign designers. Firstly, the fact that negative framing increases perceived vulnerability in the long term shows its effectiveness in attracting attention and raising awareness of climate issues. Message designers can therefore use negative framing to reinforce the perception of risk, particularly when it comes to issues that require rapid action or a change in attitude. However, the results also highlight that negative framing alone is not sufficient to increase environmental responsibility in the long term. To be truly effective, campaigns should combine messages highlighting environmental risks with concrete elements that increase self-efficacy: tutorials, examples of simple actions, feedback, practical guides or support mechanisms. By reinforcing perception, organizations increase the chances that perceived vulnerability will translate into tangible action. Furthermore, the moderating effect of self-efficacy suggests that communications should be tailored to the level of personal self-efficacy of the target audience. Individuals with high self-efficacy may respond positively to messages emphasizing risks or losses, while those with low self-efficacy may, on the contrary, develop avoidance or indifference. A segmented approach therefore seems particularly relevant: messages combining threat and empowerment for audiences that are already aware of the issue, and messages more focused on solutions, support and promoting action for more vulnerable audiences. Finally, these results encourage organizations to design continuous rather than episodic campaigns. Since perceived vulnerability evolves over time and its effect on responsibility depends on individual factors, regular, consistent, and differentiated communications help to sustainably support pro-environmental behaviors.

Although this study contributes significantly to advancing knowledge about the long-term effects of framing environmental messages, it has several limitations that are worth highlighting and that open up interesting avenues for future research. First, the sample used, consisting exclusively of students, limits the scope of the conclusions. Responses to environmental messages may vary according to age, socio-economic status or cultural background; it would therefore be relevant to broaden the diversity of participants in order to assess the robustness and transferability of the effects observed in more varied social contexts. Secondly, despite the value of a longitudinal approach, the observation period was limited to three months, which does not allow for an assessment of the sustainability of the effects beyond this time frame. Longer-term fluctuations in perceived vulnerability or environmental responsibility could emerge over extended time horizons. Future studies would therefore benefit from incorporating several additional measurement points or extending the follow-up period to better understand the temporal dynamics of behavioral responses. Finally, the use of self-reported measures is another limitation, particularly due to possible biases such as social desirability. To strengthen the external validity of the results, it would be desirable to incorporate concrete behavioral indicators, such as donation decisions, actual consumption choices, or effective engagements. Such an approach would not only overcome the limitations of self-reported measures, but also more accurately assess the real impact of messages on pro-environmental behaviors.

References

Amatulli, C., De Angelis, M., Peluso, A. M., Soscia, I., & Guido, G. (2019). The effect of negative message framing on green consumption: An investigation of the role of shame. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 157(4), 1111–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3644-x>

- Bagagnan, A. R., Ouedraogo, I., Fonta, W. M., Sowe, M., & Wallis, A. (2019). Can protection motivation theory explain farmers' adaptation to climate change decision making in The Gambia? *Climate*, 7(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli7010013>
- Bamberg, S., Masson, T., Brewitt, K., & Nemetschek, N. (2017). Threat, coping and flood prevention—A meta-analysis. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 54, 116–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2017.08.001>
- Bubeck, P., Berghauer, L., Hudson, P., & Thieken, A. H. (2020). Using panel data to understand the dynamics of human behavior in response to flooding. *Risk Analysis*, 40(11), 2340–2359. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.13575>
- Bullard, O., & Penner, S. (2017). A regulatory-focused perspective on philanthropy: Promotion focus motivates giving to prevention-framed causes. *Journal of Business Research*, 79, 173–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.06.019>
- Cacciatore, M. A., Scheufele, D. A., & Iyengar, S. (2016). The end of framing as we know it ... and the future of media effects. *Mass Communication and Society*, 19(1), 7–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15205436.2015.1068811>
- Chang, M. C., & Wu, C. C. (2015). The effect of message framing on pro-environmental behavior intentions: An information processing view. *British Food Journal*, 117(1), 339–357. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-09-2013-0265>
- Channa, N. A., Tariq, B., Samo, A. H., Ghumro, N. H., & Qureshi, N. A. (2022). Predicting consumers' intentions to purchase eco-friendly athletic wear in a moderated model of individual green values and gender. *International Journal of Sports Marketing and Sponsorship*, 23(2), 410–436. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSMS-07-2021-0128>
- Chasteen, A. L., & Madey, S. F. (2003). Belief in a just world and the perceived injustice of dying young or old. *OMEGA – Journal of Death and Dying*, 47(4), 313–326. <https://doi.org/10.2190/0QJ9-TFDP-XG5H-0TBR>
- Chen, M. Y. (2016). Consumer response to health product communication: The role of perceived product efficacy. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(9), 3251–3260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.02.024>
- Gerend, M. A., & Cullen, M. (2008). Effects of message framing and temporal context on college student drinking behavior. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 44(4), 1167–1173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2008.02.007>
- Ghanian, M., Ghoochani, O. M., Dehghanpour, M., Taqipour, M., Taheri, F., & Cotton, M. (2020). Understanding farmers' climate adaptation intention in Iran: A protection-motivation extended model. *Land Use Policy*, 94, 104553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104553>
- Gross, M., & McGoey, L. (Eds.). (2015). *Routledge international handbook of ignorance studies*. Routledge.
- Hardisty, D. J., & Weber, E. U. (2009). Discounting future green: Money versus the environment. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 138(3), 329–340. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016433>
- Kuhlicke, C., Seebauer, S., Hudson, P., Begg, C., Bubeck, P., Dittmer, C., ... Bamberg, S. (2020). The behavioral turn in flood risk management, its assumptions and potential implications. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water*, 7(3), e1418. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1418>
- Levin, I. P., Schneider, S. L., & Gaeth, G. J. (1998). All frames are not created equal: A typology and critical analysis of framing effects. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 76(2), 149–188. <https://doi.org/10.1006/obhd.1998.2804>

- Moche, H., & Västfjäll, D. (2021). Helping the child or the adult? Systematically testing the identifiable victim effect for child and adult victims. *Social Influence*, 16(1), 78–92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15534510.2021.1898400>
- Moon, S., Bergey, P. K., Bove, L. L., & Robinson, S. (2016). Message framing and individual traits in adopting innovative, sustainable products (ISPs): Evidence from biofuel adoption. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(9), 3553–3560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.01.001>
- O'Connor, R. E., Bard, R. J., & Fisher, A. (1999). Risk perceptions, general environmental beliefs, and willingness to address climate change. *Risk Analysis*, 19(3), 461–471. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.1999.tb00421.x>
- Rogers, R. W. (1983). Cognitive and physiological processes in fear appeals and attitude change: A revised theory of protection motivation. In B. L. Cacioppo & L. L. Petty (Eds.), *Social psychophysiology: A sourcebook* (pp. 153–176). Guilford Press.
- Samaddar, S., Chatterjee, R., Misra, B., & Tatano, H. (2014). Outcome expectancy and self-efficacy: Reasons or results of flood preparedness intention? *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 8, 91–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2014.02.002>
- Shafiei, A., & Maleksaeidi, H. (2020). Pro-environmental behavior of university students: Application of protection motivation theory. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 22, e00908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e00908>
- Shiv, B., Edell Britton, J. A., & Payne, J. W. (2004). Does elaboration increase or decrease the effectiveness of negatively versus positively framed messages? *Journal of Consumer Research*, 31(1), 199–208. <https://doi.org/10.1086/383434>
- Stone, G., Barnes, J. H., & Montgomery, C. (1995). Ecoscale: A scale for the measurement of environmentally responsible consumers. *Psychology & Marketing*, 12(7), 595–612. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.4220120706>
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1985). The framing of decisions and the psychology of choice. In G. Wright (Ed.), *Behavioral decision making* (pp. 25–41). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-2391-4_2
- Van de Velde, L., Verbeke, W., Popp, M., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2010). The importance of message framing for providing information about sustainability and environmental aspects of energy. *Energy Policy*, 38(10), 5541–5549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.04.044>
- Van Valkengoed, A. M., & Steg, L. (2019). Meta-analyses of factors motivating climate change adaptation behaviour. *Nature Climate Change*, 9(2), 158–163. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0371-y>
- Van Valkengoed, A. M., Perlaviciute, G., & Steg, L. (2024). From believing in climate change to adapting to climate change: The role of risk perception and efficacy beliefs. *Risk Analysis*, 44(3), 553–565. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.14102>
- Wang, Y., Liang, J., Yang, J., Ma, X., Li, X., Wu, J., ... Feng, Y. (2019). Analysis of the environmental behavior of farmers for non-point source pollution control and management: An integration of the theory of planned behavior and the protection motivation theory. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 237, 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.02.070>
- Workman, M., Bommer, W. H., & Straub, D. (2008). Security lapses and the omission of information security measures: A threat control model and empirical test. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(6), 2799–2816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2008.04.005>

Zhou, S., & Wang, Y. (2022). How negative anthropomorphic message framing and nostalgia enhance pro-environmental behaviors during the COVID-19 pandemic in China: An SEM–NCA approach. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*, 977381. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.977381>

